

Supplementary Figure 3. Transcript analysis of clonal vs. bulk PICs. (A) qRT-PCR transcript analysis of PIC markers PW1, CD34 and Sca-1 in clonal PICs, compared to bulk PICs. (B) qRT-PCR transcript analysis of pluripotency markers Oct3/4, Sox2 and Nanog in clonal PICs compared to bulk PICs. Bars represent the mean transcript copy number normalised to GAPDH. Error bars represent the standard deviation of the mean, n=3.